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FEATURES OF THE ART THERAPIST'S WORK WITH ELDERLY PEOPLE IN THE PSYCHOLOGICAL RELIEF ROOM

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In this article, we describe the pilot project of an art therapist's work with elderly people in a relief room: the case of Kryvyi Rih. The empirical study has introduced a model of psychologist retraining through an art therapy work with groups and individual therapy in the relief room. In this article, art-therapeutic programmes (group and individual) are methodologically based on the age theories of E. Erickson and R. Peck, "successful old age". Therefore, the programme is based on three blocks of art work with the structure of personality: differentiation of the Ego against the absorption of roles, transcendence of the body against the absorption of the body, transcendence of the Ego against the absorption of the Ego. For successful work, the programme of individual work uses the techniques of relaxation, imagination, phototherapy, rescripting, collage, and neurography. Collage techniques, zentagles, neurographica and neurocorrection are integrated into the group work programme.

Keywords: *art therapy, psychotherapy with elderly people, relief room.*

SPECIFICUL ACTIVITĂȚILOR DE ARTTERAPIE CU BĂTRÂNII ÎN CADRUL CAMEREI DE RELAXARE PSIHOLGICĂ

În acest articol vom discuta despre rezultatele unui studiu pilot cu referire la activitățile de artterapie cu bătrânii în cadrul camerei de relaxare (studiu de caz: or. Krivoi Rog). Studiul a constat în formarea psihologilor în artterapia individuală și de grup pentru a desfășura activități în cadrul camerei de relaxare psihologică. Programele de formare în domeniul artterapiei (individuale și de grup) au la bază teoria lui E.Erickson despre perioadele de vârstă și teoria lui R.Peck despre „bătrânețea de succes”. În acest sens, programul a constat din trei blocuri de activități de artterapie, axate pe structura personalității: diferențierea Eului versus acceptarea rolurilor; transcendența corpului versus acceptarea corpului și transcendența Eului versus acceptarea Eului. Pentru a asigura succesul activităților de artterapie, programul de terapie la nivel individual include tehnici de relaxare, imaginație, fototerapie, rescriere, colaj și neurografie, iar în activitățile de terapie la nivel de grup sunt integrate tehnici precum colajul, neurografia și neurocorecția.

Cuvinte-cheie: *terapie prin artă, psihoterapie cu bătrânii, cameră de relaxare.*

Background. Today, the legislative and executive powers in Ukraine are working to create appropriate conditions for social policy for elderly people, the conditions of which are regulated by the ratified European Social Charter (from clauses 76 to 98, of December 21, 2006) [1]. However, as of 2020, the European Committee made a comment regarding the lack of improvement in the quality and availability of social services for the elderly. In particular, it is noted that there is a need for the development of theoretically grounded and practically feasible conceptual approaches to education at an older age, the cultivation of traditions of self-education throughout life, the adaptation of educational methodologies for adults with the needs of older people, taking into account their physiology, psychology, motivation [2].

Therefore, this programme "Art therapy in the room of psychological relief" belongs to the component of the Strategy for the creation of social platforms for the participation of older people in cultural and recreational activities [3]. These are strategies for raising awareness of healthy and active aging; providing services to prevent premature aging, negative cognitive and emotional changes.

Objectives. The aim of the pilot programme is to activate the psychological forces of the elderly to improve the quality of life through art therapy sessions.

Method and procedure. The art therapy programme was created in 2021 as a pilot project for an art therapist to work with the elderly in a psychological relief room on the basis of the Territorial Centre for Social Services No.1 of the Ingulets District of the Kryvyi Rih City Council with the support of Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), the Infrastructure Programme Initiative for Ukraine, the project "Strengthening Resources for Sustainable Development of Host Communities in Eastern Ukraine". During the project, a training concept was created for specialists working in the unloading room, and training work modules were formulated [4-7]. During the main stage of the work, the goal was to practice the skills of the art therapist in the room of psychological relief, work with the equipment, work with case studies (imagination, rescripting, social atom).

In June 2021, after a preliminary conversation with psychologist, a model of practicing skills of the art therapist in the room of psychological relief was applied. This model outlines how to conduct art-therapeutic and counselling work in psychological relief room (setting, materials, principles of work with equipment, arrangement of the psychological relief room, logic of support, ethics), and refers to the following activities:

Fig.1. Model of visiting the navigation work of art therapy in the relief room.

After training work with psychologists, the final stage in the process of developing programmes was to describe the work activities that will be carried out with the whole group and with each person in particular (based on the age theories of E.Erickson and R.Peck “successful old age” [5,8]). The programmes of short-term art therapy are based on the experience of training cases and integrated the ideas of Therapeutic Thematic Arts Programming (Linda Levine-Madori, based on the integration of art techniques that inhibit brain activity of various types [9, 10]).

According to the plan, art-therapeutic programmes (group and individual) are methodologically based on the age theories of E. Erickson and R. Peck “successful old age”. Therefore, the programme is based on three blocks of art work with the structure of personality: differentiation of the Ego against the absorption of roles, transcendence of the body against the absorption of the body, transcendence of the Ego against the absorption of the Ego (Fig.2).

Fig.2. The structure of the individual art therapy program.

The group art therapy programme is based on five ideas (Fig.3):

- 1) jobs include the development of abstract expressive techniques of art therapy in conjunction with works of modern art;
- 2) to integrate exactly those isotherapy techniques that provide the obligatory aesthetics of the product with initial drawing skills (neurographics, zentagles, collages, applications and 3-D drawing).
- 3) to connect art technique with modern art and fashion for work with color therapy and sense of composition, rhythm.
- 4) for stimulation of brain activity it is important to work with spatial representations and creation of volume compositions;
- 5) to study the spectrum of emotions, it is possible to use emotion containers with therapeutic metaphors that allow you to transform the state.

Fig.3. The concept of a group program of art therapy.

The therapeutic goal (Improving the quality of life for “successful old age” of the elderly through art therapy classes in the psychological relief room) of the programmes (individual and group) and diagnostic screening to test the effectiveness of the programme was set based on the geriatric scale of depression; Spielberger test; the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC-10) and Diener Satisfaction With Life Scale (SWLS) [8].

Results. At the beginning of August 2021, the first group meeting (12 people) on art therapy took place, which was prepared before the discussion of the programme. The first lesson included diagnostics, presentation of the programme for participants with the opportunity to choose the techniques that were most responsive to group members. The group programme was adjusted according to the group's preferences. Classes in the sandbox, phototherapy and creation of mandalas from spices to zentagles, collage from textiles, and creation of felt puppet theatre were replaced.

The primary diagnostic screening was performed to test the effectiveness of the programme, which consists of a geriatric scale of depression; Spielberger test; the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC-10) and Diener Satisfaction With Life Scale (SWLS). In the following, it will be presented the results of the study of the psychological state of the group before the implementation of the programme of art therapy.

1. Geriatric Depression Scale. Assessment of depression.

Thus, according to the results shown in the table and in the figure, 91.7% (11 people) of the subjects did not show depressive tendencies. In 8.3% of subjects (1 person) the indicators correspond to the presence of a depressed state.

2. State-Trait Anxiety Inventory, STAI. Assessment of anxiety.

Thus, according to the results of the study, 16,6% of the group (2 people) has a high level of reactive anxiety, which indicates the internal tension, anxiety of the subject during group work. In 16.6% of subjects (2 people) found a low level of reactive anxiety. The other 66,8% of subjects have a moderate level of situational anxiety.

According to the results of psychological examination, 33.2% of subjects (4 persons) have a high level of personal anxiety, which indicates a persistent tendency to perceive the environment as threatening, and the manifestation of anxiety. In 66,8% of subjects found a moderate level of personal anxiety. No individuals with low levels of personal anxiety were identified.

3. Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC-10). Identifying the degree of psychological stability of the individual.

According to the results of a diagnostic study aimed at determining the degree of psychological stability, in 40.1% of subjects (5 people), the indicators are within the average. The other 59.9% have a high degree of psychological resilience, indicating optimal adaptation to environmental conditions and the ability to overcome difficulties.

4. Satisfaction With Life Scale, SWLS

According to the results of a diagnostic study aimed at determining the degree of life satisfaction, the indicators of 16,6% of the group (2 people) correspond to a low degree of subjective life satisfaction. The other 83,4 % have an average degree of satisfaction with their own lives.

Conclusions. Assessment of the pilot programme was difficult due to quarantine restrictions. However, intermediate results allow us to draw several conclusions. Even if we assumed that there would be difficulties in recruiting the group, the pilot project showed the interest and motivation of the group members for participation and, as a result, the establishment of a two-way therapeutic alliance, both in group and in pair work.

Difficulties encountered while working with the group	Success in working with the group
Inefficient distribution of time	Determining the main direction of the group
The art therapist's expectations of failure	Establishing the group's trust in the art therapist

It was assumed that phototherapy, sand therapy and the techniques of theatricalisation of puppets would become the deep techniques of working out the differentiation of the ego. However, in the process of individual or pair work, they have become environmentally friendly therapeutic methods. In group work, those methods were excluded. Consequently, we decided to connect art technique with modern art and fashion software for working with colour therapy, composition and rhythm.

We noticed that this technique was more efficient in group work, thus, afterwards, this technique was modified and repeated in several sessions at the request of the participants.

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